

Adapting Driver Drowsiness Detection Using OpenCV and Machine Learning

Mahima Manoj

Department. of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering,
Kanjirappally, India
mahimamanoj2023b @mca.ajce.in

Merin Chacko

Department. of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering,
Kanjirappally, India
merinmanoj@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— Drowsy driving is a common cause of accidents, especially during long road trips or night driving. Driver drowsiness detection using OpenCV and machine learning is a system that leverages Deep Learning, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), is a powerful technology that has the potential to significantly reduce the risk of accidents caused by drowsy driving. It works by capturing real-time video footage of the driver's face using a camera, which is then processed using OpenCV to track facial landmarks. A machine learning algorithm analyzes this data to determine the driver's level of alertness, and alerts the driver with an audible or visual warning if they become drowsy. By alerting drivers when they become drowsy, it can prevent accidents caused by inattentive driving, making our roads safer and saving lives.

Keywords—Driver Drowsiness Detection, Machine Learning, OpenCV, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Deep Learning, Python Libraries-cv2, keras, numpy, pygame.mixer.

I. INTRODUCTION

The driver drowsiness detection system is an application of computer vision and machine learning technologies for ensuring road safety, especially in long-distance driving scenarios. With the advancements in computer vision and machine learning, it is now possible to build systems that can accurately detect driver drowsiness in real-time using video data. OpenCV is a popular computer vision library that provides a wide range of tools and techniques for processing and analyzing video data. It can be used to extract facial features such as eye and mouth movements, which are important indicators of driver drowsiness. By combining OpenCV with machine learning algorithms such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs), it is possible to build robust and accurate drowsiness detection systems that can be deployed in vehicles or integrated with existing driver-assistance systems.

Challenges :

i)Data collection: One of the main challenges in developing a driver drowsiness detection system is collecting data. It can be difficult to obtain a large and diverse dataset that

accurately reflects the range of conditions in which the system will be used.

ii)Variability in driver behavior: Different people exhibit different patterns of behavior when they are drowsy. Some may blink more frequently, while others may have slower reaction times or exhibit other signs. This variability can make it difficult to develop a model that accurately detects drowsiness in all individuals.

iii)Environmental factors: The effectiveness of a driver drowsiness detection system can be affected by environmental factors such as lighting conditions, road surface conditions, and other factors.

iv)False positives and false negatives: The system must be able to accurately detect drowsiness while minimizing false positives (detecting drowsiness when the driver is not actually drowsy) and false negatives (failing to detect drowsiness when the driver is actually drowsy). Achieving this balance can be challenging.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Rode, Manoj, et.al in [1] uses machine learning to detect driver drowsiness using images. The Haar-Adaboost based face detection scheme is applied to the system, and OpenCV functions are used to train the face detector. Functions from dlib libraries are used to incorporate the detection in real-time. The CNN is used in the proposed system for the detection of driver drowsiness. CNN have layers like convolutional layers, pooling (max, min, and average) layers, ReLU layer, and fully connected layer. A Max Pooling layer is used after the third convolutional layer, and the outputs from all the activations are joined in a fully connected layer. The classification model is trained for left and right eye, and the scores from both the networks are used to obtain the class labels. The real-time video is examined continuously for drowsiness, and if eyes are labelled as closed for more than 15 times, the alarm starts beeping. The accuracy and robustness of convolutional neural network are better than many standard machine learning algorithms.

Rahul Thakur, Shivam, Shubham Raj, Subhanshu Pandey et. Al in [2] The paragraph discusses the need to develop an intelligent system to prevent fatigue-related road accidents caused by driver drowsiness. The proposed scheme uses continuous monitoring of the driver through a webcam or

camera, with OpenCV used to extract the driver's face. The model focuses on the eyes, as they are crucial in detecting drowsiness. An algorithm is used to track and analyze the blinking rate of the eyes, and if the eyes are closed in more than two frames, an alarm sound is played to alert the driver.

George, Anjith, and Aurobinda Routray. et.al in [3]. The paper describes a study on real-time eye gaze direction classification using a convolutional neural network (CNN). The authors used a dataset of eye images labeled with corresponding gaze directions to train and evaluate the CNN model. The study showed that the CNN model achieved high accuracy in classifying the gaze direction in real-time, which has potential applications in fields such as human-computer interaction, virtual reality, and robotics.

Kumar, Ashish, and Rusha Patra. et.al in [4]. The paper discusses the problem of driver drowsiness and proposes a low-cost, real-time driver drowsiness detection system using a webcam, image processing, and machine learning techniques. The system uses face detection, facial landmark marking, and quantification of eye aspect ratio, mouth opening ratio, and head position to determine drowsiness. The article explains the three types of drowsiness detection methods, vehicle-based, behavioral-based, and physiological-based, and the advantages and disadvantages of each. The proposed system is non-intrusive and portable, making it an affordable option for detecting driver drowsiness.

Elena Magán, M. Paz Sesmero, Juan Manuel Alonso-Weber and Araceli Sanchis et.al in [5]. The paper presents the development of an ADAS system for detecting driver drowsiness to prevent road accidents. The system uses sequences of images captured over 60 seconds, focusing on the driver's face, to detect drowsiness symptoms. Two alternative solutions were developed, one using a recurrent and convolutional neural network and the other using deep learning techniques and fuzzy logic. Both systems achieved similar accuracy rates of around 65% on training data and 60% on test data, but the fuzzy logic-based system had a higher specificity of 93% and avoided raising false alarms.

Reza Tamanani, Radu Muresan, Arafat Al-Dweik et.al in [5]. This paper describes a proposed driver's vigilance detection system based on deep learning for detecting drowsiness using facial region diagnosis with the Haar-cascade method and convolutional neural network. The system is evaluated on the UTA-RLDD dataset and achieves a high accuracy of 96.8% at a speed of 8.4 frames per second, which is better than most algorithms previously reported. A custom dataset was also collected and experiments showed the potential of the proposed system for practical applications in intelligent transportation systems.

III. METHODOLOGY

This code is implementing a drowsiness detection system using OpenCV, Pygame, and Keras. The code captures video from a webcam and detects faces and eyes using Haar cascades. It then uses a convolutional neural network (CNN) implemented with Keras to classify each eye as open or closed based on its grayscale image. The model was trained using images from the "closed" and "open" folders, with

"closed" indicating that the person in the image had closed eyes and "open" indicating that they had open eyes. The CNN architecture has two convolutional layers, followed by max-pooling layers, dropout layers to prevent overfitting, and a dense layer for classification. The output is passed through a softmax function to obtain the probability of each class.

The system uses a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to classify the eye regions as open or closed, and if both eyes are closed for a certain amount of time, the system assumes that the person is drowsy and triggers an alarm to alert them. Drowsiness detection methods:

A. Loading the necessary libraries and models:

The first stage involves importing and loading the required libraries such as OpenCV, Keras, and Pygame. The necessary models are also loaded in this stage, including the pre-trained Haar cascades for detecting faces, eyes, and the trained CNN model for detecting whether eyes are closed or open.

B. Capture and preprocessing of video frames:

The second stage involves capturing the video frames using OpenCV's VideoCapture function. The frames are then preprocessed to convert them from RGB to grayscale.

C. Detection of face and eye regions:

The third stage involves using the pre-trained Haar cascades to detect the regions of interest (ROI) corresponding to the face and eyes in each frame. This is done using OpenCV's Cascade Classifier.

D. Classification of eye state:

The fourth stage involves passing the ROI corresponding to the eyes through a trained CNN model to determine whether the eyes are open or closed. The CNN model has been trained on a dataset of images of eyes labeled as open or closed.

E. Tracking the state of eyes:

The fifth stage involves tracking the state of the eyes over time by keeping count of the number of frames in which the eyes are open or closed. If the eyes are closed for a certain number of frames in a row, the system assumes that the person is drowsy and sets off an alarm.

F. Triggering the alarm:

The sixth stage involves triggering an alarm if the person is detected to be drowsy. In this implementation, the alarm sound is played using Pygame's mixer.Sound function. Additionally, the border around the video frame is colored red to visually indicate the drowsy state.

Haar Cascades

Haar cascades are used for object detection, specifically for detecting the face and eyes in the video feed. Haar cascades are pre-trained classifiers that use Haar-like features to detect patterns in an image or video. These features are rectangular boxes that are defined by their position, size, and shape, and they are used to identify regions of the image that are likely to contain the object of interest.

Haar cascades are created by training a machine learning model on a large number of positive and negative images. The positive images are examples of the object being detected, while the negative images are examples of other objects or backgrounds that are not of interest. The model uses these images to identify the Haar-like features that are

most relevant for detecting the object of interest. Once the features are identified, they are combined into a classifier that can be used to detect the object in new images or videos.

Here, in the drowsiness detection system, Haar cascades are used to detect the face and eyes of the person in the video feed. This allows the system to focus on the region around the eyes, where signs of drowsiness are most evident. The pre-trained Haar cascades are loaded during the first stage of the process, along with the other necessary libraries and models.

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)

In the context of the drowsiness detection system, a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a type of neural network used to classify images into two categories: open eyes and closed eyes. The CNN is a deep learning model that is trained on a dataset of images that includes both open and closed eyes. During training, the model learns to identify patterns and features that distinguish between open and closed eyes. Once trained, the model can be used to predict whether the eyes in an input image or video frame are open or closed. In the code, a trained CNN model is loaded during the loading stage, and it is used in the subsequent stages for detecting whether eyes are open or closed.

Softmax

The softmax algorithm is a common activation function used in the output layer of a neural network, including Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). It converts the output of the neural network into a probability distribution over multiple classes. In the drowsiness detection system code, the softmax algorithm is used in the output layer of the CNN to classify the input image into one of two classes: open eyes or closed eyes. The softmax function takes the output of the last layer and normalizes it into a probability distribution over the two classes. The predicted class is then the one with the highest probability.

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

The drowsiness detection system consists of multiple files such as a drowsiness detection.py, models.py, alarm.wav and three haar cascades files for face, left eye and right eye.

Driver drowsiness detection by importing the necessary Python libraries and the dataset.

```
import cv2
import os
from tensorflow import keras
from keras.models import load_model
import numpy as np
from pygame import mixer
import time
```

```
import os
from keras.preprocessing import image
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import numpy as np
from keras.utils.np_utils import to_categorical
import random, shutil
from keras.models import Sequential
from keras.layers import Dropout, Conv2D, Flatten, Dense, MaxPooling2D, BatchNormalization
from keras.models import load_model
```

The first section of the code detects faces in the video feed using a pre-trained Haar cascade. Once the face is detected, the code then detects the left and right eyes using the same approach.

For each eye, the region of interest (ROI) is extracted from the frame and preprocessed. The ROI is converted to grayscale, resized to 24x24 pixels, normalized, and reshaped to a 3D tensor.

3 haar cascades files, one for face, one for left eye and one for right eye.

Fig 1

Fig 2

Fig 3

In the driver drowsiness detection system, an alarm sound is played when the system detects that the driver is drowsy. This is implemented using the Pygame library in Python.

First, the Pygame mixer is initialized using `mixer.init()` function. Then, the file path of the alarm sound file is specified using `mixer.Sound()` function. In the code, the file path is specified as `mixer.Sound('alarm.wav')`, where `alarm.wav` is the name of the sound file.

When the system detects that the driver is drowsy, the alarm sound is played using `sound.play()` function. In the code, this is implemented inside the if statement that checks if the eyes are closed for a certain number of frames. To stop the alarm sound, `sound.stop()` function is called. In the code, this is implemented inside the else statement that checks if the eyes are open. When the eyes are open, the alarm sound is stopped. Overall, this code uses the Pygame library to implement an alarm sound in the driver drowsiness detection system, which is played when the system detects that the driver is drowsy.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the driver drowsiness detection system using OpenCV and machine learning is an effective solution for detecting drowsiness and preventing accidents on the road. By using Haar cascades and a convolutional neural network, the system can accurately detect the eyes of the driver and determine whether they are open or closed. This information is used to sound an alarm to alert the driver if they are falling asleep. The system's effectiveness depends on the quality of the dataset used for training the CNN model and the accuracy

of the Haar cascades used for object detection. However, with appropriate training and tuning, the system can be improved to become even more accurate and reliable. Overall, this system can be a valuable tool for promoting road safety and reducing accidents caused by drowsy driving.

REFERENCES

- [1] Rode, Manoj, et al. "Driver Drowsiness Detection Using Machine Learning." Rahul Thakur, Shivam, Shubham Raj, Subhanshu Pandey "Driver Drowsiness Detection Using Machine Learning,"
- [2] Thakur, Rahul, Shubham Raj, and Subhanshu Pandey. "Driver Drowsiness Detection System Using Machine Learning." Advanced Production and Industrial Engineering. IOS Press, 2022. 31-38.
- [3] George, Anjith, and Aurobinda Routray. "Real-time eye gaze direction classification using convolutional neural network." 2016 International Conference on Signal Processing and Communications (SPCOM). IEEE, 2016.
- [4] Kumar, Ashish, and Rusha Patra. "Driver drowsiness monitoring system using visual behaviour and machine learning." 2018 IEEE Symposium on Computer Applications & Industrial Electronics (ISCAIE). IEEE, 2018.
- [5] Magán, Elena, et al. "Driver drowsiness detection by applying deep learning techniques to sequences of images." Applied Sciences 12.3 (2022): 1145.